

AUTOMATED ATTENDANCE SYSTEM (USING RFID TECHNOLOGY)

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ABSTRACT

In 2010, the UK Border Agency (UKBA) introduced a procedure to guide College and university on how to govern international students (under tier 4 point based system) which involves taking a closer look at student's progress during the period of their stay i.e. with the use of attendance. This idea was accepted because attendance system provides numerous benefits to the educational institutions, exposing the lecturer to the rate of student attendance during lecture hours as this will help providing student with the support, assistance and advice they need during their course. However, there is a down side to implement this procedure as the present system of attendance is manually handled. This paper introduces a technology that can eliminate the drawbacks of the present system and also providing a user-friendly environment, saves time and provides accurate data.

Keywords: Time and attendance system, RFID technology and contactless smart card.

INTRODUCTION

The 20th century is the era of information, the management of information requires the accurate collection of data. The ability to manage information and time leads to increase in productive levels and the achievement of set goals. The slogan "Information is power" is very much true as information helps in the decision making which could either help to make or break any organization despite past successes, the same principle works in the education institute as the whereabouts of students within an education institute at certain times gives the management an idea of certain activities within the institute. An education institute is a place where different individuals with different mindsets, level of understanding and purpose, comes together to share and expand their knowledge. While expanding their knowledge, effective management of student's progress starts with the collection of accurate attendance. To collect these attendance, manual data collection is employed using paper time cards and time sheets filled out by students under the supervision of the lecturer but the challenges of the manual data collection (especially in a high populated class) are time consuming and tedious, data loss, data neglect and error prone (Uddin, et al., 2014). However, with the introduction of technologies like Automatic Identification System, information is accurately retrieved and stored without human errors. Automatic identification system according to MHI (2016) is also called Automatic identification and data collection, AIDC, Auto id, Automatic Data Capture and Data Collection is a family of technologies that identify, verify, record, communicate and store information on discrete, package items. Duncan and Yossi (2003) defined Automatic Identification System as "an information system that identifies each physical item in an automated and timely manner. The real time available of item identity allows other information relative to the item to be drawn on in an order to access both the current state of the product and future actions required". According to Margaret, (2016) "Automatic Identification and Data Capture is a broad category of technologies is used to collect information from an object, image or sound without manual data entry". Engineers Garage (2012) stated that "Automatic Identification and Data Capture refers to the method of automatically identifying objects, collecting data about them and entering that data directly

into a computer system (i.e. without human involvement)". while Automated Identification Data Capture Technology (AIDC) is known for the purpose of automated identification of items or humans and the management of information; these includes how information is gathered, collected, manipulated, distributed and stored. AIDC comes as a problem solver when it comes to the collection of accurate data speedily and effectively either by little or no human interaction. Smart cards, voice recognition, optical character recognition, fingerprint and optical strip, Radio frequency identification and Barcode are some of the subsets of AIDC. In this paper, Radio frequency identification (RFID) is the technology we focus on, it comprises of the reader, Tags and its Database and it is capable of offering a link between a real-life event with an actual moving object at real time. for example, the movement of students in and out the classroom can be capture. (Akpınar and Kaptan, 2010; Jerry, 2012).

RELATED WORKS

A compact and reliable classroom attendance system using RFID and face verification was proposed by Bhaskar (2016), the RFID system identifies the student using the RFID card (RFID uniquely identifies the student based on the card number) and further identity verification of the student is carried out using face recognition technique which then uses an individual (Fast Adaptive Neural Network Classifier – FANNC) classifier is used to verify the face of each student exclusively. Konatham, et al (2016) also propose a new model for parent alerting and automatic attendance marking using of RFID (Radio- Frequency Identification) and GSM (Global System for Mobile Communication) to enable automated and reliable attendance, informing parents and school administration about the student using a unique RFID card with a micro controller attached to the classroom door. Kuriakose and Vermaak (2015) proved that there is a high correlation between high class attendance and academic performance Using Java based Radio Frequency Identification Technology (RFID) application as an automate attendance monitoring. Other applications of the RFID technology. Daud and Yahya (2009) used the RFID technology as a smart document tracking system. Alyami and Atkins (2016) proposed a system to improve hospital management using RFID and ZigBee technologies for tracking and monitoring patients.

PROPOSED SYSTEM

A. System Overview

The present system captures data by manual collection where students are given a paper sheet with their names and initials printed on it. This method gives room for students to sign in for their friends and in the case of name initial, some students have the same initial which can cause mistakes leading to inaccurate attendance information. The use of the proposed system eliminates the errors caused by the present system. The proposed system comprises of the reader, tags installed in student identification cards and a database, an application is installed in the lecturer's system to retrieve the attendance read by the reader. This attendance is stored in the database along with time of entry and time of departure.

Fig. 1. The basic diagram of the proposed system.

B. System Architecture

The schematic diagram of the proposed system is shown in Fig. 2. This system employs both hardware and software components. The hardware components are the reader and the tags while the software component comprises of the database and the application used to translate radio signals read by the reader. The translated signals are processed, filtered and stored in the database.

Fig 2. A schematic diagram of the proposed Student's time attendance

C. Flow of Operation

The tags in the student identification cards are woken by the reader whenever they are at reading range. In every tag, there is a unique number, information of the student and an encrypted key. The tags can be decrypted by the reader that has the decrypt key, this is a security function to protect the information on every tag. If the reader can not decrypt the key on the tag, the information will not be read by the reader but if that's not the case, the information on the tag is read and validated.

Fig 3. The proposed system first section of the flow of operation.

The application receives encrypted information from the communication Programming Interface, it decrypts the received information, checks for correctness and then stores it in the System's Database

Fig 4. The proposed system second section of the flow of operation.

The user interface application is the user friendly part of the system that allows the lecturer check and retrieve information stored in the Database. The Lecturer has the option of viewing the combination of all attendance for a selected module or just the attendance of a particular student. The application also provides the option of printing the attendance or sending an excel format file as an attached file to any destination (via email, WhatsApp etc.).

Fig

5: A descriptive diagram of the proposed system.

IMPLEMENTATION

The hardware required are RFID reader, RFID Tags used as user identification tool for attendance collection and a computer. The programming languages required to connect the hardware to the database are Net, Java, php etc.

Table 1. Comparison between the Present and Proposed System

	Present system	Proposed system
Accuracy	Low	High
Data Accessibility	Hard	Ease
Physical storage space	Large (it will include storage room)	Small (Database or a cloud storage)

RESULTS

The proposed system introduces a significant advantage of the use of Radio frequency technology (RFID) as a mechanism for enhancing accuracy attendance collection. The figure below shows the reaction of students, parents and lecturers to the proposed system.

Fig 6: A chart showing various end user's reaction to the proposed system

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This paper introduces a student based Time Attendance System that uses RFID Technology as the key component for collecting attendance data. RFID technology helps to provide accurate data along with the time the student enters and leaves the class. The proposed system also provides a medium where attendance data is accessed easily and on time. Other automated identification technology can be added to support the proposed system as this will provide more authenticated data.

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